

Variation in thermal tolerances of the Argentine ant

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Declaration

I, the undersigned, hereby declare that the work contained in this thesis is my own original work and that I have not previously in its entirety or in part submitted it at any university for a degree.

Signature.....

Date.....

Abstract

The Argentine ant, *Linepithema humile* (Mayr) is one of the most significant invasive insect species, indigenous to South America but currently distributed across many parts of the world. It has been reported to have several negative influences on the local biodiversity of the areas it has invaded and therefore poses a serious conservation threat to many biomes. Consequently, understanding the factors that limit the abundance and distribution of this species at local to global scales is important. Laboratory and field studies have identified temperature and water availability as two of the most significant factors influencing Argentine ant abundance and distribution. Although water balance characteristics of the Argentine ant have been thoroughly investigated, less attention has been given to the thermal physiology from the perspectives of absolute tolerances, inherent limits to activity, and performance at different test temperatures. Indeed only a single study on the upper lethal limits of this species exists to date, while lower critical thermal and lower lethal limits have not been investigated. In addition, despite concerns over the wide range of experimental rates of temperature change that are in use in thermal tolerance studies today, no study has investigated the effects of such rates on the outcome of acclimation for both upper and lower critical thermal limits. Here I make a start at providing this information for the Argentine ant by examining upper and lower lethal limits (Chapter 2), critical thermal limits to activity (Chapter 3), and the responses of these traits to acclimation. Furthermore, because lethal limits are dependent on exposure duration, I examined exposure duration x test temperature interactions in this species.

In the case of lethal limits (Chapter 2), acclimation temperatures significantly influenced both upper and lower lethal limits. Upper lethal limits varied between 37 and 44 °C, whilst lower lethal limits varied between -4 and -10.5 °C, with an acclimation effect more pronounced for upper than lower lethal limits. This finding suggests that upper thermal limits likely contribute to distributional limits whereas lower thermal limits do not, at least for this species. Second, a significant time by exposure temperature interaction was found for both upper and lower lethal limits, with a more pronounced effect of acclimation temperatures at longer exposure durations. In other words, mortality rates increased with longer exposure durations. This finding is in agreement with

previous studies that have documented poorer thermal tolerances with extended exposure duration to stress.

The results from Chapter 3 show that acclimation temperatures significantly influenced critical thermal limits but the magnitude of acclimation responses varied considerably with the rate of temperature change used in the experiments. While the magnitude of acclimation responses declined with faster rates for CT_{Max} , the reverse was true for CT_{Min} thus indicating that both traits differ from each other in their responses to acclimation temperatures. Second, in both traits, the shape of frequency distribution curves became narrower as inter-individual variability decreased with faster rates of temperature change. This finding has important implications for further assessments of vital characteristics of thermal tolerance traits such as heritability. Third, contrary to other studies, slower rates of temperature change did not induce any hardening responses in the Argentine ant.

In conclusion, this thesis provides insight into the thermal physiology of the Argentine ant, which up to date has been poorly represented in insect physiological studies.

Opsomming

Die Argentynse mier, *Linepithema humile* (Mayr), inheems aan Suid Amerika, is een van die mees prominente indringer spesies en huidiglik oor groot dele van die wêreld verspreid. Verskeie negatiewe effekte op die inheemse biodiversiteit van die area wat dit ingedring is is aangeteken en dus 'n ernstige bedreiging inhou vir baie biome. Dus is dit belangrik om die faktore wat die getalle en verspreiding van die mier beperk te verstaan, plaaslike en internasionale. Laboratorium en veld studies het temperatuur en waterbeskikbaarheid geïdentifiseer as twee van die belangrikste faktore wat die Argentynse mier se volopheid en verspreiding beïnvloed. Hoewel die waterbalans eienskappe van die Argentynse mier deeglik ondersoek is, is minder aandag gegee aan die termiese fisiologie vanuit die perspektief van absolute toleransie, natuurlike limiete en prestasie by verskeie toets temperature. Daar is inderdaad slegs 'n enkele studie oor die hoër terminale limiet tot op hede, terwyl die laer kritieke limiet en laer terminale limiete geensins ondersoek is nie. Verder, benewens die bekommernisse oor die wye reeks van eksperimentele tempos van temperatuur verandering wat gebruik word in termiese toleransie studies vandag, het geen studie die effekte van hierdie tempos op akklimasie op beide die hoër en laer kritieke termiese limiete ondersoek nie. Die studie maak 'n begin in die voorsiening van hierdie informasie vir die Argentynse mier deur hoër en laer terminale limiete te bestudeer (Hoofstuk 2), kritieke temperatuur limiete tydens aktiwiteit, (Hoofstuk 3) sowel as die reaksie van hierdie eienskappe op akklimasie. Verder, omdat terminale limiete afhanklik is van die tydperk van blootstelling, is die blootstellingstydperk x toets temperatuur interaksies ondersoek in hierdie spesie.

In die geval van terminale limiete (Hoofstuk 2), het akklimasie temperature beide die hoër en laer terminale limiete betekenisvol beïnvloed. Hoër terminale limiete het varieer tussen 37 en 44 °C, terwyl onderste terminale limiete varieer het tussen -4 and -10.5 °C, met 'n akklimasie effek wat meer beduidend was vir die hoër as die laer terminale limiet. Hierdie bevinding stel voor dat die hoër temperatuur limiete, en nie die laer limiet nie, moontlik bydrae tot die verspreidings grense, in hierdie spesie. Tweedens, 'n betekenisvolle tyd by blootstellingstemperatuur interaksie is gevind vir beide die hoër en onderste terminale limiete, met 'n meer beduidende effek van akklimasie temperature na langer blootstellingstydperke. Dus, mortaliteits tempos het toegeneem met langer

blootstellingstydperke. Hierdie bevinding is in ooreenstemming met vorige studies wat swakker termiese toleransies aangeteken het, met uitgebreide blootstelling aan stres.

Die resultate van Hoofstuk 3 wys dat akklimasie temperature die kritieke termiese limiete betekenisvol beïnvloed, maar die mate van akklimasie reaksies het aansienlik verskil ten opsigte van die tempo van temperatuur verandering wat in die eksperimente gebruik is. Terwyl die mate van akklimasie reaksies afgeneem het met vinniger tempos van temperatuur verandering vir CT_{Max} , was die teenoorgestelde waar vir CT_{Min} , wat daarop dui dat die eienskappe van mekaar verskil in hulle reaksies ten opsigte van akklimasie temperature. Tweedens, in beide eienskappe word die vorm van die frekwensie verspreidingskurwe smaller soos wat inter-individu variasie afneem met vinniger tempos van temperatuurverandering. Hierdie bevinding het belangrike implikasies vir verdere ondersoek van termiese toleransie eienskappe soos oorerflikheid. Derdens, in teenstelling met ander studies, het stadiger tempos van temperatuur verandering nie enige verhardings reaksies in die Argentynse mier tot gevolg gehad nie.

Ter afsluiting, die tesis voorsien insig in die termiese fisiologie van die Argentynse mier, wat tot op hede swak verteenwoordig was in insek fisiologiese studies.

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Dedication

To my parents; Gertrude Bonglam and Kenjo wan Jumbam (both of blessed memory).

INCLUDE ME IN

I do not ask for a place
in the front row;
keep me far down below
because I know my weakness.

Admit me right at the back
when St. Peter locks the gate,
only let him lock me in.

The race is wearisome
even for those who can run;
I know my endurance
and lack of concentration.

Often I'm swayed by side attractions,
but push me, I plead, across the line,
across the winning line on time.

When the results are read,
my name cannot figure
in the first group for sure;
nor even in the middle grade.

Let it come in the last group,
in the very tail end,
but pray, include me in the list.

Kenjo Jumbam

Nkambe,
7th July, 1991.

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Chapter 1

General Introduction

The different ways in which animals respond to temperature change have received renewed attention in recent years partly because of global warming and its possible impacts on individual fitness, population dynamics, ecosystem structure and function as well as on distribution and abundance of species (Berrigan, 2000; Parmesan et al., 2000). Increasing atmospheric concentrations of greenhouse gases have resulted in an increase in global temperatures (IPCC, 1998; 2001) by ~ 0.6 °C on average, over the past century (Walther et al., 2002). Extreme weather events including unusually low or high temperatures have been recorded with increasing frequency in many countries around the world (Parmesan et al., 2000; Somero, 2005). These climatic changes are accompanied by changes in species phenologies such as early egg-laying dates (Crick and Sparks, 1999), and shifts in species ranges towards the poles (Parmesan et al., 1999; Parmesan and Yohe, 2003) which may then result in shifts in the physiological adaptations of the species (Ghalambor et al., 2007).

Climate change is expected to have profound effects on invasive species and their interactions with indigenous species (Dukes and Mooney, 1999; Calosi et al., 2007; Chown et al., 2007). This is because the increase in temperature with global warming is predicted to be suitable for invasive species that are capable of tolerating a wide range of microclimates and thus able to outperform indigenous species that are more sensitive to climate change (Dukes and Mooney, 1999). For example, on sub-Antarctic Marion Island, where mean annual temperature has increased by more than 1 °C over the last 50 years and annual rainfall has decreased by more than 500 mm (Smith, 2002), both desiccation and thermal tolerances differ between indigenous and invasive collembolans (Chown et al. 2007, Slabber et al. 2007). Cold acclimation favours desiccation resistance in indigenous species, whereas warmer acclimation temperatures favour this trait in invasive species (Chown et al. 2007). Upper Lethal Temperature₅₀ (ULT₅₀, the temperature at which 50 % of mortality was recorded) is significantly higher in invasive (33-37 °C) than in indigenous species (30-33 °C), while crystallisation temperatures (supercooling points, T_c) are lower in indigenous (c. -20 to -13 °C) than in invasive species (c. -12 to -6 °C) (Slabber et al., 2007). These findings again support the prediction that global warming will favour invasive over indigenous species.

Although the Argentine ant is one of the most widespread invasive species that has been predicted to expand its distribution ranges with global warming (Roura-Pascual et al., 2004) remarkably very little is known about its physiology (but see Walters and Mackay 2003, 2004).

Study species

The Argentine ant, *Linepithema humile* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) is indigenous to South America (Wild, 2004) but it is currently distributed across many countries around the world (Roura-Pascual et al., 2004), including South Africa. The Argentine ant is thought to have been accidentally introduced into South Africa via Cape Town during the Anglo-Boer war, when fodder probably containing nests of this species was transported from South America as food for the British horses (Skaife, 1955). Its distribution across South Africa remains largely unknown (Skaife, 1953). The first record of the Argentine ant in Stellenbosch was in 1901 (Prins et al., 1990), and it has since been reported to have negative influence on the local biodiversity (Bond and Slingsby, 1983; Christian, 2001). For example, the Argentine ant is known to displace indigenous ant species and other ground-dwelling invertebrates (Carpintero et al., 2003; Walters and Mackay, 2003; Blancafort and Gomez, 2005; Tillberg et al., 2007), including ecologically important seed eating and dispersal species (Christian, 2001; Holway et al., 2001; Gomez and Oliveras, 2003; Gomez et al., 2003). The Argentine ant therefore poses a conservation threat to many biomes (Gomez and Oliveras, 2003; Lach, 2007).

In introduced ranges, the Argentine ant forms large, single colonies with multiple queens per nest and unlike in their indigenous ranges, nest-mates are often not aggressive towards each other (Holway et al., 1998; Suarez et al., 1999; Silverman and Nsimba, 2000; Tsutsui et al., 2001; Holway and Suarez, 2004; Jaquiery et al., 2005). This limited aggression between Argentine ant nest-mates in introduced populations partly accounts for its success as an invasive species because it is able to establish and disperse across vast areas (Passera, 1994). The mode of dispersal of the Argentine ant is another important factor contributing to its success as an invasive species. Dispersal of Argentine ants takes place through natural and human-mediated means (Holway, 1995; Suarez et al., 2001; Carpintero et al., 2003). Individuals disperse naturally by colony budding, a

process by which some queens and workers leave the mother nest to establish a new nest elsewhere, covering an average distance of ~150 meters per year (Suarez et al., 2001; Holway et al., 2002a). This is a slower means of dispersal compared with human-assisted dispersal whereby longer distances are covered within relatively shorter periods of time. For example, by the accidental transportation of Argentine ant nests or individuals in vehicles, ships and even by aircraft (Skaife, 1953; Slingsby 1982; see also Holway, 1995).

Within both its introduced and indigenous ranges, the distribution of the Argentine ant is influenced by several abiotic factors (Witt and Giliomee, 1999; Vega and Rust, 2001; Walters and Mackay, 2003; Krushelnycky et al., 2005), of which two are most significant. First, relative humidity is known to have a significant influence on the Argentine ant. For example, survival of Argentine ant populations in the laboratory was greatest when relative humidity of their environment exceeded 90 % (Walters and Mackay, 2003). Another laboratory study by Holway et al. (2002b) showed that survival of Argentine ant workers was highest when ≥ 20 ml of water was added to their colonies daily. In the field, elevated soil moisture not only increases survival of the Argentine ant, but also increases its chances of invading new areas and of displacing indigenous ant communities (Holway et al., 2002b; Menke and Holway, 2006). The Argentine ant occurs in moist environments along river banks, streams and coastal areas (Holway, 1995; Ward, 1987), suggesting that the species is susceptible to desiccation. Indeed, Schilman et al. (2005) showed that the Argentine ant had significantly higher rates of water loss both through the cuticle and spiracles in comparison with four indigenous ant species from southern California.

The second most important abiotic factor influencing Argentine ant distribution is temperature. Field experiments showed that the Argentine ant stopped foraging when soil surface temperatures exceeded 44 °C (Witt and Giliomee, 1999), suggesting that it is sensitive to high temperatures. Laboratory studies showed 100 % mortality of the Argentine ant at temperatures between 45 and 47 °C in comparison to only 50 % mortality at 50 °C in the indigenous Australian ant species *Iridomyrex rufoniger* (Walters and Mackay, 2004). The Argentine ant thus shows reduced survival and activity with increasing temperatures relative to indigenous ant species (Walters and Mackay, 2004).

Despite the numerous studies on abiotic factors influencing the abundance and distribution of the Argentine ant, only a few papers have considered its physiology. These works have investigated the thermal biology of development and oviposition rate (Hartley and Lester, 2003; Abril et al., 2008), the effects of desiccation on the workers of this species relative to those of other ants (Schilman et al., 2005, 2007), and aspects of the response of Argentine ants to desiccation and to high temperature (Human et al., 1998; Walters and Mackay, 2003, 2004). Typically, however, despite the focus of many modelling and behavioural studies on the importance of temperature as a limiting abiotic factor (Roura-Pascual et al., 2004, 2006; Krushelnycky et al., 2005), such work has been cursory and restricted in its scope. Nonetheless studies on the physiological responses of the Argentine ant to abiotic factors such as temperature are important for understanding the traits that make it a successful invader. In addition, such studies are needed to complement previous and future studies on the ecology and genetics of this species. Furthermore, survival and distribution of the Argentine ant in the face of global warming can be predicted with more certainty if its physiological responses to climatic parameters such as temperature are known.

Thermal tolerances and their experimental designs

Physiological processes in animals are influenced by many factors, of which temperature is one of the most important (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a; Chown and Nicolson, 2004). Temperature sets upper and lower limits to animal function (Vannier, 1994; Angilletta et al., 2002, 2006; Somero, 2005) and the measurement of thermal tolerances is an important first step in understanding the range of temperature conditions under which an animal might be active (Vannier, 1994; Angilletta et al., 2002, 2006). Thermal tolerances are measured in two major ways namely, the dynamic and the static methods (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a, b). The static method is used in lethal temperature assessments and is a measure of percentage survival in groups of animals (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a; Chown and Nicolson, 2004; Deere et al., 2006) while the dynamic method used in critical thermal limits assays assesses the upper and lower temperature limits to animal function (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997b; Deere et al., 2006; Terblanche et al., 2007). In one dynamic method, animals are warmed

or cooled at a constant rate until the onset of muscle spasms in the case of upper thermal limits (also called critical thermal maxima or CT_{Max}) (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a, b), or the onset of chill coma in the case of lower thermal limits (critical thermal minima or CT_{Min}) (reviewed in Chown and Terblanche 2007). Upper and lower lethal temperatures (ULT and LLT respectively) are static measures of tolerance, assessed in the laboratory by exposing groups of individuals to a set temperature for a fixed period after which individuals are returned to their original thermal environment and percentage survival is assessed after several hours (Chown and Nicolson, 2004). In many studies, percentage survival is assessed after a minimum of 24 h (e.g. Deere et al., 2006, Slabber et al., 2007) which is considered sufficient to detect some of the longer-term effects of test temperature on individual fitness, which may not be immediately detectable following exposure to a given temperature (Chown and Nicolson, 2004).

Although both critical thermal limits and lethal temperatures are measures of thermal tolerance, they differ in the traits they reflect as well as in the experimental designs required to measure them (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a, b). The ease with which critical thermal limits are measured has resulted in the more frequent use of this method in temperature tolerance assessments (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a). However, lethal temperature assays are equally important in thermal tolerance assessments. Lethal temperature assays (also called mortality assays) are associated with high stress levels and are important in assessing non-mobile (e.g. pupae) stages, or highly mobile (e.g. winged adults) stages, that are either restricted to a given habitat or that may not be able to use any form of behavioural response such as flight to escape extreme temperatures (Chown and Nicolson, 2004).

Responses of thermal tolerances to acclimation

Thermal tolerance traits can respond in a variety of ways to different acclimation temperatures. For example, acclimation may enhance thermal tolerances to stressful temperatures and consequently improve survival of individuals (Hoffmann, 1995). The ability of an animal to alter its fitness and to express different phenotypes as a consequence of biotic and abiotic factors is referred to as phenotypic plasticity (Kingsolver and Huey, 1998; Agrawal, 2001). Acclimation is a form of phenotypic

plasticity (Chown and Terblanche, 2007) and acclimation responses are defined as “reversible modifications of an organism’s physiology that could last from minutes to months, occurring in anticipation of future changes in their surroundings or as a consequence of experimentally induced environmental conditions experienced in the laboratory” (Huey and Berrigan, 1996). Similar reversible changes in an organism’s physiology that occur in its natural environment are referred to as acclimatization (Chown and Nicolson, 2004).

Many studies have shown that in insects, acclimation has a more pronounced influence on lower than on upper thermal tolerances suggesting that resistance to heat and cold are decoupled. For example, in a study by Klok and Chown (2003) investigating resistance to high and low temperatures in ten sub-Antarctic weevils species, they found a greater acclimation response in CT_{Min} than in CT_{Max} (see also Chown, 2001). Addo-Bediako et al. (2000) compiled data on both upper and lower lethal limits to investigate variation in thermal tolerances of species across latitudinal gradients. Their study showed that upper and lower thermal tolerances were decoupled and that latitudinal variation in lower thermal limits was twice as wide (~60 °C range) as in upper thermal tolerances (~30 °C range). On a regional scale, the altitudinal variation in critical thermal limits of several dung beetle species was investigated and the results also showed a greater variation in CT_{Min} in comparison with CT_{Max} across a 2400 m altitudinal gradient (Chown, 2001; see also Gaston and Chown, 1999). Therefore, in insects, the general trend observed is that of greater phenotypic plasticity in lower than in upper thermal tolerances.

In most physiological studies however, the influence of experimental design on thermal tolerances has received little attention. For example, in the case of critical thermal limits, one of the most important concerns has been the use of a wide range of heating and cooling rates in many studies (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a) and yet few studies have documented the possible effects of different rates on thermal tolerances.

Given this background, the present thesis is concerned with the thermal biology of Argentine ant workers. Specifically, it is concerned with both upper and lower critical thermal limits (two dynamic traits) and upper and lower lethal temperatures (two static traits). Moreover, the response to acclimation of both sets of traits is investigated. This

work forms the focus of Chapter 2. In Chapter 3, the influence of heating and cooling rates and their interaction with acclimation temperatures on critical thermal limits is investigated using Argentine ant workers as a model system. These methodological issues have not been explored well in the literature.

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Chapter 2

Lethal temperatures and their responses to acclimation in the Argentine ant:
Exposure duration by test temperature interactions

Introduction

Thermal tolerance assessments are essential for understanding the range of temperatures under which species might be active and consequently determine the geographic ranges and population dynamics of species (Ghalambor et al., 2006; Calosi et al., 2007). Thermal tolerances are measured in two major ways namely, the dynamic (see Chapters 1 and 3) and the static methods (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a, b). The static method is used in lethal temperature assessments, otherwise called mortality assays (Chown and Nicolson, 2004). The static method involves either maintaining a constant temperature and varying exposure time or keeping exposure time constant while varying test temperature until survival ranges between 0 and 100 % (see Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a; Chown and Nicolson, 2004; Deere et al., 2006). The static method is also used to determine values which represent the temperatures where 50 % (LT₅₀) of the population survives (Fry et al., 1942; Burks and Hagstrum, 1999; Deere et al., 2006).

Assessment of lethal temperatures of species has declined over the past years (see Fig. 1a, Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a) partly because this method of thermal tolerance assessment requires large sample sizes and is more time consuming than the dynamic method (Sømme, 1999; Galbreath et al., 2004; Mora and Maya, 2006). Furthermore, it has been argued that stress levels in lethal temperature assessments are more severe than in the dynamic method (Hoffmann et al., 1997; Sørensen and Loeschcke, 2001). However, both methods of assessing thermal tolerances are important because not only do they differ in their methodology, but also in the traits they measure (Chown and Nicolson, 2004; Chown and Terblanche, 2007). While the dynamic method is used to measure thermal limits to animal function (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a, b), the static method assesses percentage survival in batches of animals subjected to a given temperature for a fixed duration (Deere et al., 2006). In addition, each thermal assessment method is associated with different genes and underlying mechanisms (Sørensen and Loeschcke, 2001). That is, both methods are genetically independent (but see Berrigan, 2000). For example, Hoffmann et al., (1997) investigated different measures of heat resistance in selected lines of *Drosophila melanogaster* and found that selection had a significant effect on knockdown resistance but not on survival in mortality assays or on individuals assessed singly.

Although it has been argued that stress levels experienced by organisms during non lethal thermal assays are less severe and more likely to be encountered in nature than stress levels at mortality assays (Hoffmann et al., 1997), the latter remains a vital method of assessing thermal tolerances. Mortality assays are especially useful in evaluating non-mobile (e.g. pupae, larvae) or highly mobile (e.g. winged adults) insects that are either restricted to a given habitat or that may not be able to escape extreme temperatures by using any form of behavioural response such as flight (Chown and Nicolson, 2004). Lethal temperature assays of such insects that are unable to escape extreme conditions are important in providing an estimate of the time for which a given stressful temperature might be endured (Chown and Nicolson, 2004; Slabber et al., 2007). Therefore, despite the decline in lethal temperature assays (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a), these assays are important and necessary for understanding the physiological responses of insects to thermal stress.

There are many factors that have been shown to influence lethal temperature assessments of which acclimation temperature is one of the most important. In a study by Slabber et al., (2007), higher acclimation temperatures resulted in an increase in ULT₅₀ (i.e. the upper temperature where 50 % of the population survived) in invasive springtail species but either caused a decline or did not significantly influence ULT₅₀ of indigenous species. In the sub-Antarctic psocid *Antarctopsocus jeanneli* Badonnel, acclimation to 0 °C significantly lowered LLT₅₀ (i.e. the lower temperature where 50 % of the population survived) from -7.7 °C in field fresh individuals to -13 °C (Slabber and Chown, 2004). Acclimation to low temperatures (0 °C and -10 °C) in the species *Sitophilus granarius* and *Cryptolestes ferrugineus* respectively, have been shown to increase cold tolerance and consequently survival time, by more than ten-fold in both species (Fields et al., 1998). Acclimation temperature effects on lethal temperatures have been investigated in some marine and terrestrial mite species from sub-Antarctic Marion Island using wet and dry treatment groups (Deere et al., 2006). While LLT₅₀ declined significantly with lower acclimation temperatures in dry treatment groups of marine species, acclimation had a weak effect on wet LLT₅₀ treatment groups of both marine and terrestrial species (Deere et al., 2006). In the tropical beetle *Alphitobius diaperinus*, two weeks acclimation to 15 °C significantly increased the duration of survival in these beetles, with 100 % mortality

recorded after 22 days in comparison with 10 days in nonacclimated beetles (Renault et al., 2004). In young goldfish, upper lethal temperatures have been shown to increase with increasing acclimation temperatures in the ratio of 1:3 while lower lethal temperatures declined with acclimation temperature in the ratio of 2:3 (Fry et al., 1942). In other words, acclimation temperatures had a more pronounced effect on lower than on upper lethal temperatures in goldfish (Fry et al., 1942). Interestingly, this pattern of less variation in upper than in lower thermal tolerances as a consequence of acclimation has been documented in insects across geographic (Addo-Bediako et al., 2000) and regional scales (Chown, 2001; Klok and Chown, 2003).

Gender is another factor that has been shown to influence lethal temperature assessments. For example, in the encephalitis vector *Culiseta incidens*, the time taken for 50 % of individuals to die was consistently shorter in males than in females at all test temperatures (Su and Milla, 2001) meaning that in these mosquitoes, the males are more sensitive to temperature than the females. Likewise, gender and age have been shown to have significant effects on thermal tolerances in a range of *Drosophila* species (Hoffmann et al., 2003). Hence gender and age are important factors to consider in mortality assays.

Exposure duration to potentially lethal temperatures is one of the most important factors determining mortality rates of many insects (Cossins and Bowler, 1987; Sømme, 1999; Chown and Nicolson, 2004). For example, extended exposure durations have been shown to result in poorer thermal tolerances at both upper and lower temperatures in the tsetse fly *Glossina pallidipes* (Terblanche et al., 2007; also see Chapter 3). Mortality rates have also been shown to increase with exposure duration and test temperatures in the moth parasitoid *Habrobracon hebetor* (Carrillo et al., 2005). A decline in survival with extended exposure times is of significant ecological importance because it means sub-lethal temperatures may become lethal if exposure duration is extended (Bale, 1993; Chown and Nicolson, 2004; Terblanche et al., 2007). Hence, interactions between exposure duration and test temperatures ultimately determine mortality rates (Cossins and Bowler, 1987; Sømme, 1999). However, exposure duration by test temperature interactions have been poorly studied in insect physiology despite the importance of such

studies in the better understanding of insect thermal tolerances. Therefore the aims of this Chapter were two fold:

- To investigate lethal temperatures and their responses to acclimation temperature in the Argentine ant.
- To investigate the influence of exposure duration by test temperature interactions on mortality rates in the Argentine ant.

Materials and methods

Laboratory acclimation and maintenance of ant populations

Argentine ant populations were collected from around Stellenbosch (33°55'S 18°51'E) and brought into the laboratory within 2 h where they were immediately acclimated at one of four temperatures (15, 20, 25, 30 °C) for a minimum of seven days. Seven days was selected as the minimum acclimation period because this duration has been shown to be sufficient for the full development of acclimation responses in thermal tolerance traits in several arthropod species (e.g. Hoffmann and Watson, 1993; Klok and Chown, 2003; Terblanche et al., 2006, 2007).

Each acclimated population consisted of ~500 workers housed in plastic containers (20 × 11 × 8 cm) lined with fluon (Northern Products, Woonsocket, Rhode Island, USA) to prevent ants from escaping (Holway et al., 2002; Walters and Mackay, 2003, 2004). The Argentine ant is sensitive to relative humidity (Walters and Mackay, 2003; Menke et al., 2007; Schilman et al., 2007) and in order to minimize desiccation stress, distilled water was freely available to ant populations in the form of moistened cotton wool. In addition, containers housing ant nests were enclosed in larger plastic containers (25 × 25 × 14.5 cm) lined with a sheet of moistened cotton wool to maintain high relative humidity during acclimation. Ants were fed pin-head crickets once every second day (Suarez et al., 2001; Holway et al., 2002; Lighton et al., 2004; Schilman et al., 2005) while 16.7 % (w:v) sucrose solution and distilled water were provided *ad libitum*. During acclimation, each population was frequently moved between shelves to prevent within-chamber acclimation effects. Acclimation chambers were set to 12L:12D photoperiodic cycle.

Only workers (sterile females) were used in experiments because of four main reasons. First, they are the most abundant caste (Vega and Rust, 2001) and as such, large sample sizes for thermal limit assessments were not a limiting factor. Second, the possibility of gender effect on experimental results was eliminated because workers are all females. Third, they are easily distinguishable from the other castes because they are not as large as the queens and are not winged as are the males (Passera and Keller, 1994; Vega and Rust, 2001). Fourth, the worker ants are all similar in size which will minimize the potential effects of size, mass or volume on heat exchange.

As mentioned above, age is another important factor to consider in mortality assays. However, age is a difficult parameter to evaluate in ants and therefore the exact age of individuals used in experiments could not be determined. Nonetheless, newly emerged workers (easily identified by their lighter colour) were excluded from all experiments and care was taken to select only very active, healthy individuals for experiments.

Lower and upper lethal temperatures

For both lower and upper lethal temperature assessments (LLT and ULT respectively), a static method was employed (see Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a, b) whereby five batches consisting of 10 ants each were submerged in a programmable water bath (Grant LTC12, Grant Instruments, Cambridge, UK) at a set temperature, for a fixed period (30 min, 1 h, 2 h, 4 h). Soft paintbrushes were used to collect live ants into batches of ten after preliminary trials with CO₂ anaesthesia gas resulted in high mortality and impaired locomotion, even at mild test temperatures of 25 °C and after only 30 min exposure durations (personal observations). In both ULT and LLT assessments, batches of ants were placed in (9 × 1.5 cm) cylindrical plastic vials, with moist cotton wool in mesh-covered screw tops of each cylinder to eliminate desiccation stress. After exposure of batches to a set test temperature, individuals were transferred to a recovery vial at the original acclimation temperature. The recovery vials consisted of a 60 ml propylene vial per batch of ants, with moistened cotton wool in mesh-covered perforated lids to prevent desiccation of ants. All recovery vials were then placed in plastic containers (25 × 25 × 14.5 cm) based lined with a sheet of moist cotton wool before returning to original

acclimation temperatures, thus maintaining a near 100 % relative humidity. Animals were scored for survival after 24 h and survival was considered as coordinated movement while moribund state or no movement were scored as mortality.

Temperature of the water bath was either increased (ULT) or decreased (LLT) by 1 °C and the assessment repeated with a new set of individuals until the percentage of survivors varied between 100 and 0 % for all four exposure times (30 min, 1 h, 2 h and 4 h) and acclimation temperatures (15, 20, 25 and 30 °C). For both traits, a logistic regression was used to calculate LT_{50} values (the temperature where 50 % of the population survived) but this procedure only applied where the logistic regression provided a significant fit to the data based on Wald statistics (Quinn and Keough, 2002). Mean \pm SE LT_{50} was then calculated across the five repeats for each time period and each acclimation temperature and a generalized linear model was used to investigate the effects of time and acclimation temperature on LT_{50} . In addition, to visualize better the thermal limits of the ants, contour plots of percentage survival at each time by test temperature, for all acclimation temperature were plotted onto a single surface using a distance weighted, least squares interpolation in Statistica v. 7.

Results

Lower lethal temperatures (LLT_{50})

There was a positive relationship between exposure duration and LLT_{50} (Fig. 1) meaning that the temperature at which 50 % of the population survived was progressively milder with extended exposure duration. Acclimation temperature had a significant effect on LLT_{50} (Table 1) but an increase in acclimation temperatures did not correlate with an increase percentage mortality, as would have been expected (Fig. 1). Rather, percentage survival was greatest at intermediate acclimation temperatures (20 and 25 °C) with the lowest LLT_{50} values of approximately -11.5 °C recorded at 30 min exposure duration of the 25 °C acclimation group. Percentage mortality was greatest at extreme acclimation temperatures (i.e. 15 and 30 °C) with the mildest LLT_{50} value of -3 °C recorded at 4 h exposure duration of the 30 °C acclimation group, closely followed by -4 °C at 4 h exposure duration and at 15 °C acclimation group. Clearly, mortality rates of the

Argentine ant were significantly influenced by acclimation temperatures and exposure duration by test temperature interactions (Table 1).

Upper lethal temperatures (ULT₅₀)

In the case of ULT₅₀, longer exposure durations resulted in lower ULT₅₀ values (Fig. 2) indicating that longer exposure durations had a significantly negative effect on percentage survival (Table 1). There was a negative relationship between acclimation temperatures and ULT₅₀ for the 4 h exposure, meaning that ULT₅₀ decreased with warmer acclimation temperatures (Fig. 2). The lowest ULT₅₀ values across all exposure durations were inconsistent, but for the 4 h exposure duration this was found at 30 °C acclimation temperature. Acclimation temperatures by exposure durations interactions were also significant (Table 1) and percentage mortality increased significantly with longer exposure durations. Generally, individuals were able to tolerate temperatures between -5 to -10 °C and 40 to 45 °C (Fig. 3).

Table 1. Outcome of generalized linear models (normal distribution, identity link function) exploring the effects of acclimation temperature and exposure duration on ULT₅₀ and LLT₅₀, respectively.

Effect	χ^2	df	p
ULT₅₀			
Acclimation	92.1	3	0.0001
Duration	244.0	3	0.0001
Acclimation x Duration	110.8	9	0.0001
Deviance/df	11/64 = 0.17		
LLT₅₀			
Acclimation	125.0	3	0.0001
Duration	240.1	3	0.0001
Acclimation x Duration	53.7	9	0.0001
Deviance/df	13/64 = 0.20		

Fig. 1 Effect of acclimation temperatures and exposure durations on LLT₅₀ using a generalized linear model assuming a normal distribution with an identity link function.

Fig. 2 Effect of acclimation temperatures and exposure durations on ULT₅₀ using a generalized linear model assuming a normal distribution with an identity link function.

Fig. 3 Contour plot showing percentage survival (in increments of 20 %) for each of the test temperatures at each duration of exposure across the full set of acclimation treatments. 100 indicates complete mortality, whilst 0 indicates complete survival of a sample of workers.

Discussion

Acclimation temperature, exposure duration and the interactions between acclimation temperature and exposure duration all significantly influenced percentage survival in the Argentine ant. This is the first study to have explicitly investigated the effects of a wide range of acclimation temperatures and exposure durations on percentage survival of the Argentine ant. In many similar studies, exposure duration is often limited to 1 h (e.g. Slabber and Chown, 2004; Deere et al., 2006; Slabber et al., 2007). In this study, ULT₅₀ values obtained for 1 h exposure duration ranged from 39.6 to 42.3 °C across all acclimation treatments. These ULT₅₀ values are similar to those documented in other invertebrate studies with a similar experimental protocol. For example, a study investigating the lethal temperatures of five mite species from sub-Antarctic Marion Island acclimated to temperatures ranging from 0 °C to 15 °C showed that ULT₅₀ values varied between species from 36.1 to 40.7 °C (Deere et al., 2006). Other studies have investigated upper thermal tolerances in the Argentine ant using methods that differ from the one used in this study. For example, Holway et al., (2002) placed non-acclimated Argentine ant workers in glass test tubes plugged with moistened cotton and then exposed them to a 12 °C range of temperatures to determine their tolerances to high temperatures. They recorded 50 % mortality at ~45 °C after 1 h exposure duration. Differences in experimental design could account for the higher ULT₅₀ values in their study in comparison to ≤ 42.3 °C documented in my study. In yet another study on upper thermal tolerances in the Argentine ant, a similar protocol to that used by Holway et al., (2002) was used and survivorship of workers was determined by counting numbers of live and dead individuals after 1, 2 and 3 h (Walters and Mackay, 2004). They found 100 % mortality after 3 h exposure to 47 °C (Walters and Mackay, 2004). Although this protocol was not implemented in this study, it is clear that the Argentine ant is sensitive to high temperatures. Indeed, the lowest ULT₅₀ values (36.5 °C) were obtained at the warmest acclimation temperature in my study while cooler acclimation temperatures tended to have higher ULT₅₀ values. Overall, ULT₅₀ tended to be closer to those found for many ant species (e.g. Heatwole and Harrington, 1989; Francke et al., 1985), slightly lower than that recorded for Argentine ant workers collected in Adelaide, Australia

(Walters and Mackay, 2004), and considerably lower than highly thermophilic species (e.g. Christian and Morton, 1992).

In the case of lower lethal temperatures, extreme acclimation temperatures (15 °C and 30 °C) had the most pronounced negative effects on percentage survival than the intermediate acclimation temperatures. This suggests that there are costs associated with acclimation of the Argentine ant to extreme temperatures. It has been shown in *Drosophila melanogaster* that acclimation to high temperatures results in a decrease in fecundity and increased larval mortality (Krebs and Loeschke, 1994; Krebs and Feder, 1997; 1998).

The LLT₅₀ values obtained in this study varied across acclimation temperatures from -3.0 to -11.2 °C which are higher than those from sub-Antarctic Marion Island springtail species that varied from -6.4 to -20.8 °C (Slabber et al., 2007) which is not surprising considering the fact that the Argentine ant is sensitive to temperature extremes. The values from this study were however in the same range as those from wet and dry treatments of sub-Antarctic Marion Island mite species which had LLT₅₀ values ranging from -3.7 to -11.6 °C across four acclimation temperatures from 0 to 15 °C (Deere et al., 2006). In the sub-Antarctic psocid *Antarctopsocus jeanneli* LLT₅₀ values ranged from -7.7 °C in field fresh individuals to -13.0 °C in 0 °C acclimated individuals (Slabber and Chown, 2004).

More importantly, is the influence that exposure duration has on both upper and lower lethal temperatures in this study. Although it has been suggested that exposure duration could play a significant role in the survival ability of animals (Cossins and Bowler, 1987; Sømme, 1999), studies documenting the impact of duration on percentage survival are scarce. In both upper and lower lethal temperatures, percentage mortality in the Argentine ant increased significantly with exposure duration. In conclusion, acclimation temperatures had a significant effect on both upper and lower lethal temperatures of the Argentine ant but the trends in responses to acclimation differed between the two traits (see Fig. 1 and 2). In addition, percentage mortality increased at milder temperatures with prolonged exposure durations.

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Chapter 3

Effects of rates of temperature change on the acclimation responses of critical thermal limits

Introduction

Temperature is an important climatic parameter that affects the fitness of populations (Vannier, 1994; Angilletta et al., 2002, 2006; Somero, 2005). Body temperature of ectotherms such as insects generally varies with environmental temperature (Neven, 2000; Angilletta et al., 2006). Therefore, measurement of thermal tolerances is an important first step in understanding the range of temperature conditions under which an insect might be active (Vannier, 1994; Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a; Angilletta et al., 2002, 2006). The activity range of a species provides useful insight into possible effects of environmental temperature changes on the ecology, distribution ranges, population dynamics and evolution of the species (Ghalambor et al., 2006; Calosi et al., 2007; Chown and Terblanche, 2007).

When assessing thermal tolerances of a species either in the laboratory or in the field, factors influencing such assessments should be taken into consideration. The thermal history of a species will likely influence its thermal tolerance, particularly the thermal environment of the species in the days closest to its thermal tolerance assessments (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a; Gaston and Chown, 1999). Hence, investigating acclimation temperature effects on thermal tolerances is important because acclimation temperature can greatly influence physiological responses of insects. Acclimation is defined as reversible, facultative changes to the phenotype (Wilson and Franklin, 2002), resulting from exposure to a new, experimentally induced, environmental condition (Woods and Harrison, 2002). Acclimation temperature is known to influence thermal tolerances of many insects. For example, low acclimation temperatures have been shown to decrease chill coma recovery time and mortality in *Drosophila melanogaster* (Rako and Hoffmann, 2006). Acclimation temperature has also been shown to influence thermal tolerances in beetles (Terblanche et al., 2005) and tsetse flies (Terblanche et al., 2006), whereby upper critical thermal limits showed less variation with acclimation temperature than lower critical thermal limits (also see Chown, 2001). This trend of less variation in upper thermal tolerance than in lower thermal tolerance in insects has been documented at regional (Gaston and Chown, 1999) and global (Addo-Bediako et al., 2000) scales. Interestingly, this trend has recently been documented in some spider species (Jumbam et al., 2008), whereby upper critical thermal

limits varied by ~ 0.4 °C compared with ~ 1 °C at lower critical thermal limits. However, the only other study to have investigated the influence of acclimation temperature on thermal tolerances in spiders found no acclimation effect on upper critical thermal limit, the only temperature tolerance trait examined in the study (Seymour and Vinegar, 1973). Similarly, acclimation temperatures had no effect on both upper and lower thermal tolerances of some European diving beetles (Calosi et al., 2007), indicating that the influence of acclimation temperatures on thermal tolerances vary among traits and taxa (see Chown and Terblanche, 2007 for review).

Time of day has been shown to influence thermal tolerance assessments. For example, significantly greater larval mortality at night than during the day as a result of temperature differences between day-time and night-time has been documented in beetles (McMillan et al., 2005). The developmental stage of insects can also influence thermal tolerances, as is the case in some beetle species whose larvae had lower supercooling points than their adult stages (Rossolimo, 1997). In addition, the developmental stage of acclimated species has been shown to influence thermal tolerances in tsetse flies (Terblanche and Chown, 2006) and in kelp flies (Terblanche et al., 2007a). Furthermore, the use of certain gases to sedate insects may also influence experimental outcome. For example, carbon dioxide anaesthesia significantly increased chill coma recovery time in *Drosophila melanogaster* when exposure duration to this gas exceeded 60 min (Nilson et al., 2006). Similarly, carbon dioxide anaesthesia has been shown to impair locomotion in cockroaches (Branscome et al., 2005). Other factors that could possibly influence thermal tolerance assessments include gender, feeding status, age and pregnancy.

Whilst the above factors should be, and are increasingly being addressed in insect thermal biology literature, other important factors directly linked with experimental design such as rate of temperature change, have enjoyed much less attention (but see Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a; Chown and Nicolson, 2004). The two major experimental designs used to evaluate thermal tolerances in insects are the static and dynamic methods (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a). The static method, often used in assessing lethal temperatures (see Chapter 2 for detailed discussion), involves either maintaining a constant temperature and varying exposure time or keeping exposure time constant while varying temperature until survival varies between 0 % and 100 % (see

Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a; Chown and Nicolson, 2004; Deere et al., 2006). This method is used to determine values which represent the temperatures where 50 % of the population survives (LT_{50}) (Fry et al., 1942; Deere et al., 2006). On the other hand, the dynamic method involves changing test temperature at a constant rate until the species under investigation exhibits a functional limit e.g. knockdown, onset of muscle spasms, loss of righting response (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997b; Deere et al., 2006; Terblanche et al., 2007b).

Critical thermal limits, assessed using the dynamic method, are the high and low temperature limits to animal function. The dynamic method is often preferred by most researchers to lethal temperature assessments because, unlike the latter, the dynamic method requires fewer animals and is less time consuming (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a; see also Galbreath et al., 2004; Mora and Maya, 2006). The ease with which critical thermal limits are measured (Chown and Nicolson, 2004; Galbreath et al., 2004; Mora and Maya, 2006) has unfortunately resulted in the use of different experimental protocols by some researchers (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a; Chown and Nicolson, 2004) such as the use of varied equilibration or start temperature (Terblanche et al., 2007b). Equilibration temperature refers to the “constant temperature during which animals are held before heating or cooling, to allow equilibration of body temperature with ambient temperature” (Terblanche et al., 2007b). Although equilibration temperature has been varied in experimental protocols, its effects on critical thermal limits are only recently being acknowledged. For example, in the tsetse fly *Glossina pallidipes*, high equilibration temperatures resulted in the largest upper critical thermal limit values whilst low equilibration temperatures resulted in the lowest lower critical thermal limit values (Terblanche et al., 2007b).

The rate of temperature change in critical thermal assessments remains one of the most varied elements of the dynamic experimental design. The rate of temperature change refers to cooling (i.e. CT_{Min} assessments) or heating (CT_{Max} assessments) individuals until failure of physiological function in the form of knockdown, loss of righting response or muscle spasms (Terblanche et al., 2007b). Although the influence of rates of temperature change on thermal tolerances has been previously highlighted (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison, 1997a), few studies have explicitly evaluated the influence

of cooling and/or heating rates on critical thermal limits. Even so, documented studies of this nature have seldom looked at more than a single trait in the same individual. Rather, emphasis has been on the effects of cooling rates on lower thermal tolerances (Chown and Nicolson, 2004). For example, the effects of four different cooling rates on survival in *Drosophila melanogaster* show that survival was least at the slowest cooling rate which was 0.01 °C/min, partly due to low-temperature stress (Overgaard et al., 2006). On the other hand, survival was greatest at the ecologically relevant cooling rate of 0.05 °C/min, due to an increase in the degree of membrane lipid unsaturation, resulting in improved cold tolerance (Overgaard et al., 2006). Other studies show that slow cooling rates allow individuals to rapidly cold harden, resulting in the survival of otherwise lethal temperatures (Kelty and Lee, 1999, 2001; Rako and Hoffmann, 2006; Worland et al., 2007). Cold shock due to exposure to acute temperatures often results in insect mortality due to cell membrane transition from liquid-crystalline phase to lethal gel phase (Drobnis et al., 1993; Tomčala et al., 2006; Chown and Terblanche, 2007). Death as a result of cold shock is prevented in rapidly cold hardened flies *Sarcophaga bullata* due to a significant increase in their membrane fluidity, a mechanism that prevents cell injury and death (Lee et al., 2006).

Despite the advantages of slow cooling rates on survival, more studies are needed to determine how widespread this trend is in insects. Moreover, there is evidence to suggest that slow cooling rates do not necessarily result in enhanced cold tolerance in some species. For example, Terblanche et al., (2007b) investigated the effect of rates of temperature change on both upper and lower critical thermal limits of the tsetse fly *Glossina pallidipes* and found that in both traits, faster rates resulted in improved thermal tolerances while the reverse was true at slower rates. However, because so few studies have investigated the influence of rates of temperature change on thermal tolerances, a firm conclusion cannot be made at this stage on the emerging trends of responses to cooling rates.

Far fewer studies have documented the influence of heating rates on thermal tolerances, with the majority of studies mainly on fish (Galbreath et al., 2004; Mora and Maya, 2006). Even so, the findings have been contradictory. While faster heating rates resulted in higher critical thermal limits in the fish species *Salvelinus fontinalis*

(Galbreath et al., 2004) the reverse was true in the fish species *Acanthemblemaria hancocki* which had reduced levels of thermal tolerance at faster heating rates (Mora and Maya, 2006).

Despite the above differences in response to thermal tolerances, it is clear that the rate at which an animal cools or warms up has a profound influence on its survival ability (Ramløv, 2000; Sinclair, 2001; Chown and Nicolson, 2004). Secondly, studies demonstrating how different rates of temperature change can influence thermal responses of multiple traits in a single individual are important to understanding how experimental design can influence thermal tolerances. To date, no study has explicitly investigated the effects of experimental rates of temperature change on the outcome of acclimation for both upper and lower critical thermal limits.

In addition, effects of rates of temperature change on the mean and variances of critical thermal limits have received little attention despite the importance of such investigations in understanding how natural selection works. Natural selection is a process that influences frequency distribution of heritable traits (Bech et al., 1999) in three major ways: by altering the trait mean without changing trait variance, by maintaining a constant trait mean but decreasing the trait variance, or by altering the trait mean and variance (Endler, 1986). These three major ways by which natural selection influences frequency distributions of traits are termed directional, stabilizing and disruptive selection, respectively (Endler, 1986).

In all three selection types, interactions between trait mean and trait variance are important in understanding what drives natural selection of heritable traits. Therefore investigating rate of temperature change effects on the mean and variances of traits is essential to understanding trait heritability in species.

Here, I make a start at addressing the above gaps in literature by investigating the effects of four rates of temperature change on the mean, variance and acclimation responses of upper and lower critical thermal limits in the Argentine ant, *Linepithema humile*. I chose the Argentine ant because it is an invasive species (Holway, 1998a, b; Tsutsui and Case, 2001; Suarez et al., 2001; Roura-Pascual et al., 2004), with temperature and humidity being major determinants of its distribution (Walters and Mackay, 2004; Menke and Holway, 2006), and it is easily reared and maintained in the laboratory (Baker

et al., 1985; Ward, 1987; Holway et al., 2002; Walters and Mackay, 2003, 2004), making it a good model species for experimental studies.

Material and methods

Animal collection and acclimation

Argentine ant populations were collected from Stellenbosch (33°55'S 18°51'E) in the Western Cape province of South Africa and brought into the laboratory (usually within 1 h) where they were acclimated at 15, 20, 25 or 30 °C for a minimum of seven days. We chose a minimum acclimation period of seven days because this period has been shown to be sufficient for the full development of acclimation responses in thermal limits in many invertebrates (e.g. Hoffmann and Watson, 1993; Klok and Chown, 2003; Terblanche et al., 2006).

Each acclimated population consisted of ~500 worker individuals housed in plastic containers (20 × 11 × 8 cm) lined with fluon (Northern Products, Woonsocket, Rhode Island, USA) to prevent ants from escaping (Holway et al., 2002; Walters and Mackay, 2003, 2004). The Argentine ant is sensitive to relative humidity (Walters and Mackay, 2003; Schilman et al., 2007) and to minimize desiccation stress, distilled water was freely available to each of the four acclimated populations in the form of moistened cotton wool. In addition, bigger plastic containers (25 × 25 × 14.5 cm) were base-lined with a sheet of moistened cotton wool, upon which the smaller containers housing ant nests were placed prior to acclimation. Ants were fed pin-head crickets once every second day (Suarez et al., 2001; Holway et al., 2002; Lighton et al., 2004) while drinking water and 16.7 % (w:v) sucrose solution were freely available on a daily basis. During the acclimation period, each population was frequently moved between shelves to prevent within-chamber acclimation effects. Acclimation chambers were set to 12L:12D photoperiodic cycle.

Only workers (sterile females) were used in experiments for four main reasons. First, they are the most abundant caste (Vega and Rust, 2001) and therefore large sample sizes for thermal assessments were not a limiting factor. Second, the possibility of gender effects on experimental results was eliminated because workers are all females. Third, females are easily distinguishable from the other castes (Passera and Keller, 1994; Vega

and Rust, 2001). Fourth, the worker ants are all similar in size which will minimize the potential effects of size, mass or volume on heat exchange.

Age is another important factor that could influence thermal tolerance assessments. However, because age is a difficult parameter to evaluate in ants, the exact ages of individuals used in experiments could not be determined. Nonetheless, newly emerged workers (easily identified by their lighter colour) were excluded from all experiments and care was taken to select only very active, healthy individuals for experiments.

Critical thermal limits

An insulated double-jacketed system which consisted of 11 isolation chambers for individual ants was connected to a programmable water bath (LTC 12 Grant Instruments Ltd., Cambridge, UK) which regulated water temperature around the chambers (similar to the methods described in Klok and Chown, 2003). The start temperature for all critical thermal limits experiments was 25 °C, thereby eliminating any possible influence of variations in start temperatures on experimental outcome (see Terblanche et al., 2007b). Ten ants were placed singly into the chambers and a 40-gauge copper-constantan (Type T) thermocouple connected to an electronic thermometer was inserted into a control chamber to monitor chamber temperatures. Based on their small body sizes (mean \pm 1 S.D.; 0.5 ± 0.1 mg, $n = 20$), the body temperature of the insects was considered equivalent to that of the chamber. After 6 min equilibration time, temperature was increased (CT_{Max}) or decreased (CT_{Min}) at a constant rate of either 0.05, 0.1, 0.25 or 0.5 °C/min ($n = 50$ per rate and per trait) until the endpoint was observed, defined as the onset of muscle spasms in the case of CT_{Max} (Lutterschmidt and Hutchison 1997b) and loss of coordinated muscle function in the case of CT_{Min} (see Chown and Terblanche, 2007).

Statistical analysis

Shapiro-Wilks tests were used to determine whether or not data were normally distributed. Because data were not normally distributed in a few cases, effects of rates of temperature change and acclimation temperatures on CT_{Max} and CT_{Min} were investigated

using a generalized linear model assuming a normal distribution and using an identity link function (Quinn and Keough, 2002). Bartlett's test was used to assess the extent to which variances differed among the rate groups within each acclimation temperature.

Results

Acclimation responses

Acclimation temperature had a significant influence on CT_{Max} (Table 1). However, the magnitude of acclimation responses varied considerably with heating rate (Fig. 1a). For example, at 0.05 °C/min, the magnitude of acclimation response was ~3 °C by comparison with ~1 °C at 0.5 °C/min.

Similarly, acclimation temperature significantly influenced CT_{Min} and again, acclimation responses were rate-dependent (Table 1). However, unlike in CT_{Max} , the magnitude of acclimation responses increased with faster cooling rates (Fig. 1b). For example, at 0.05 °C/min the magnitude of acclimation response was ~1 °C in comparison with ~3 °C at 0.5 °C/min. In other words, acclimation x rate interactions had significant effects on both upper and lower critical thermal limits.

Rate effects on trait variances

Rate of temperature change had a considerable effect on the range of variation in trait responses among individuals in each of the four acclimation groups. For CT_{Max} , inter-individual variability was greatest at the slowest rate of temperature change (Fig. 2). For example, in the 15 °C acclimation group, there was 10 °C variation among individuals at 0.05 °C/min in comparison with only 2 °C variation at 0.5 °C/min (Fig. 2). This range of inter-individual variation among rate treatments was statistically significant (Fig. 2) and similar for each of the acclimation groups.

Similarly, in CT_{Min} , inter-individual variability was greatest at 0.05 °C in all four acclimation temperatures investigated (Fig. 3). For example, in the 15 °C acclimation group, CT_{Min} varied among individuals by 8 °C at 0.05 °C/min by comparison with 3 °C variation at 0.5 °C/min (Fig. 3). This range of inter-individual variation among rate treatments was similar in all acclimation groups.

Table 1. Outcome of generalized linear models (normal distribution, identity link function) exploring the effects of acclimation temperature and warming or cooling rate on CT_{Max} and CT_{Min} , respectively.

Effect	χ^2	df	p
CT_{Max}			
Acclimation	148.6	3	0.0001
Rate	1372.4	3	0.0001
Acclimation x Rate	174.5	9	0.0001
Deviance/df	1305/774 = 1.68		
CT_{Min}			
Acclimation	244.3	3	0.0001
Rate	441.3	3	0.0001
Acclimation x Rate	157.8	9	0.0001
Deviance/df	621/774 = 0.80		

Hardening responses

If a hardening response takes place, one might expect as rates decline, tolerance to extremes is improved. By contrast, CT_{Max} increased with faster heating rates while CT_{Min} decreased with faster cooling rates in all four acclimation temperatures (Fig. 4). In other words, thermal tolerances to potentially lethal temperatures improved with shorter exposure durations and faster rates of temperature change in both traits and across all acclimation temperatures. Therefore, no effect of hardening was found.

Fig. 1a. Effects of rates of temperature change on critical thermal maxima (CT_{Max}) across four acclimation temperatures using a generalized linear model assuming a normal distribution with an identity link function. Means ± S.E. are shown and n ~ 50 for each acclimation temperature.

Fig. 1b. Effects of rates of temperature change on critical thermal minima (CT_{Min}) across four acclimation temperatures using a generalized linear model assuming a normal distribution with an identity link function. Means \pm S.E. are shown and $n \sim 50$ for each acclimation temperature.

Fig. 2. Effects of rates of temperature change on inter-individual variability in CT_{Max} across all four acclimation temperatures.

Fig. 3. Effects of rates of temperature change on inter-individual variability in CT_{Min} across all four acclimation temperatures.

Fig. 4a. Scatter plot of experimental duration against mean critical thermal maxima (CT_{Max}). The lines fitted by least-square regression illustrate differences in direction between rates and traits. Letters denote rates of temperature change (a = 0.5 °C/min; b = 0.25 °C/min; c = 0.1 °C/min; d = 0.05 °C/min).

Fig. 4b. Scatter plot of experimental duration against mean critical thermal minima (CT_{Min}). The lines fitted by least-square regression illustrate differences in direction between rates and traits. Letters denote rates of temperature change (a = 0.5 °C/min; b = 0.25 °C/min; c = 0.1 °C/min; d = 0.05 °C/min).

Discussion

In agreement with previous studies, acclimation clearly has an effect on both CT_{Max} and CT_{Min} . Previous studies that also document acclimation temperature effects on thermal tolerances include a study by Slabber and Chown (2005) where they documented ~ 3.3 °C increase in CT_{Min} of adult *Halmaeus atrimors* induced by acclimation temperatures ranging from 0 °C to 20 °C over seven days acclimation period. Similarly, Terblanche et al., (2006) documented ~ 3.3 °C increase in CT_{Min} of *Glossina pallidipes* induced by a 19-29 °C acclimation temperature range over ten days. It is well known that in insects, CT_{Min} varies to a greater extent with acclimation temperature than CT_{Max} (e.g. Chown, 2001; Klok and Chown, 2003; Slabber and Chown, 2005; Terblanche et al., 2006). Although this trend of greater variation in lower than in upper thermal tolerances has been documented on both global (Addo-Bediako et al., 2000) and regional (Gaston and Chown, 1999; Chown, 2001) scales, most studies have typically used a single rate of temperature change (Klok and Chown, 2001, 2003; Terblanche et al., 2006; Sinclair et al., 2006) in assessments of thermal tolerances. The few studies that have assessed rate effects on thermal tolerances have either focused only on lower (Overgaard et al., 2006; Rako and Hoffmann, 2006; Worland et al., 2007) or upper (e.g. Galbreath et al., 2004; Mora and Maya, 2006) thermal tolerances. In the only study where the effects of rates on both traits have been assessed (Terblanche et al., 2007b) acclimation effect was not investigated.

This is the first study documenting the interaction between rate and the extent of acclimation response. This study showed that both heating and cooling rates had a pronounced effect on the acclimation response. The fastest rate had the highest acclimation effect on CT_{Min} whereas the lowest rate had the highest acclimation effect on CT_{Max} . This has implications for understanding the extent to which upper and lower thermal limits differ in their responses to acclimation. To date, most studies have used rates of change in the region of 0.25 °C/min to 0.5 °C/min (see reviews in Hoffmann et al., 2003; Chown and Nicolson, 2004; Chown and Terblanche 2007), and have documented more flexibility in CT_{Min} than in CT_{Max} . If lower rates of change had been used perhaps the opposite situation might have been found. At least in this study, this is

the case. However, it might well not have been the case in investigations of species such as *Drosophila melanogaster* where hardening takes place during slow rates of temperature change. What the outcome will be of further studies that vary rates of change during acclimation studies is difficult to tell, but it seems unlikely that large-scale patterns will be entirely affected because they are also based on other measures of tolerance (reviewed in Chown, 2001). However, when assessing the extent to which tropical vs temperate organisms show phenotypic plasticity, rate effects will have to be carefully investigated.

In addition to these effects on the mean values, the shape of the frequency distribution was also profoundly affected by the rate of warming or cooling. The most significant implications of this effect on variance are not only analytical, but also more importantly, on the estimate of heritability of the traits in question. If one assumes relatively consistent relatedness among nest-mate workers (acknowledging polygyny in the Argentine ant) (Tsutsui and Suarez, 2003), then changes in the total variance as a consequence of rate variation will affect total phenotypic variance, but not genetic variance. Recalling that broad sense heritability is calculated as:

$$\sigma_g^2 / \sigma_p^2 \tag{1}$$

then an increase in the total phenotypic variance owing to experimental conditions will result in lower estimates of heritability of the trait in question (see Hartl, 1980).

Thus, the results from this study demonstrate that the rate of temperature change used in an experiment has two critical and underappreciated effects: first, the estimate of the mean of critical thermal limits varies considerably, which might also reflect a similar response to different rates in the field. Second, and more importantly, the shape of the frequency distribution becomes narrower with faster rates. This means that further assessments of important characteristics of traits such as heritability, will be affected substantially by the temperature change rate adopted.

Contrary to previous studies (e.g. Kelty and Lee, 1999, 2001; Rako and Hoffmann, 2006; Worland et al., 2007), an increase in experimental duration as a result of slow rates of temperature change did not result in heat or rapid cold hardening during

CT_{Max} and CT_{Min} experiments respectively (Fig. 4). Rather, animals performed worst with increasing experimental duration, reaching thermal limits at milder temperatures. In the case of CT_{Max} , the reasons for a decline in this trait with prolonged exposure duration are not entirely clear partly because not so many studies of this type exist in insects (Chown and Nicolson 2004). The few studies available either document a similar trend to what I found in this study, for example in the tsetse fly *Glossina pallidipes* (Terblanche et al., 2007b) or the contrary, as in the ant *Myrmecocystus depilis* (Kay and Whitford, 1978). In view of these contradictory findings and the fact that so few studies of this nature exist in insects, the reasons for a decline in CT_{Max} with increasing exposure duration in the Argentine ant are not entirely known. However, the extent of temperature-induced injury in an organism is positively related to the duration and magnitude of the stress and may eventually lead to death (Chown and Nicolson, 2004). Therefore, as a consequence of the rates of temperature change implemented in this study, exposure duration and the magnitude of stress influenced the tolerance of the Argentine ant. As experimental duration increases, other factors such as starvation and dehydration may negatively influence survival and confound any hardening responses in the Argentine ant. Overall, this study suggests that the Argentine ant is incapable of heat hardening.

Similarly, an increase in CT_{Min} (i.e. poor thermal tolerance) with prolonged exposure duration indicates the lack of a rapid cold hardening response in the Argentine ant. Previous studies assessing rapid cold hardening in insects (e.g. Kelty and Lee, 1999, 2001; Lee et al., 2006; Overgaard et al., 2006; Rako and Hoffmann, 2006; Worland et al., 2007) give reasons such as an increase in membrane fluidity that prevents cell injury and death, thus improving thermal tolerances of sub-zero temperatures in the insects investigated. Clearly, this mechanism does not apply to the Argentine ant because individuals reached CT_{Min} at milder temperatures with slower rates and prolonged experimental duration. The similar reasons for lack of heat hardening (e.g. starvation, dehydration, low-temperature stress) may be responsible for lack of rapid cold hardening in the Argentine ant. Even more important is that the interactions between exposure duration and temperature (Ramløv, 2000; Terblanche et al., 2007b) have been shown to influence mortality rates in other species and may well be the case here. In other words, the ability to survive a temperature is significantly influenced by the amount of time

spent at that temperature. Hence even milder temperatures become lethal at prolonged exposure durations thus increasing mortality rates as is the case in the Argentine ant.

In conclusion, this study highlights several important points; first, that acclimation responses depend on experimental rate of temperature change; second, that the estimate of mean and variances in critical thermal limits change considerably with experimental rate adopted; and third, that contrary to previous studies, slower rates of temperature change do not necessarily induce thermal hardening. In consequence, further assessments of important characteristics of critical thermal limits such as heritability, will be affected to a large extent by the methodological approach adopted. Therefore, more thought is needed when choosing experimental rates and in interpreting results thereof.

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Chapter 4

General Conclusions

The overall objective of this study was to investigate variation in thermal tolerances of the Argentine ant. In most physiological studies, thermal tolerances are assessed by dynamic or static methods, both of which were employed in this thesis. Chapter 2 involved assessing thermal tolerances in the Argentine ant by the static method. As previously mentioned, the static method is a less commonly used, yet highly important method of assessing thermal tolerances. The decline in popularity of the static method has been attributed to large sample size requirements, high stress levels experienced by animals, as well as the fact that this method is more time consuming than the dynamic method (see David et al., 1998; Chown and Nicolson, 2004). Nonetheless, it has been argued that lethal temperature assays differ from critical thermal limits assessments in the traits they measure, and that lethal temperatures provide an estimate of the time for which a stressful condition may be endured by insects that encounter extreme temperatures daily (Hoffmann et al., 2003; Chown and Nicolson, 2004; Rako et al., 2007). Since exposure duration is a key factor in determining mortality rates in animals, this study aimed to investigate exposure duration x test temperature interactions in the Argentine ant. In addition, the effects of acclimation on ULT₅₀ and LLT₅₀ (i.e. the upper and lower lethal temperatures where 50 % of the population survived) were investigated.

The data presented here show that longer exposure durations significantly increased mortality rates, which is similar to previous studies (Cossins and Bowler, 1987; Sømme, 1999). In addition, acclimation temperature had a significant effect on both ULT₅₀ and LLT₅₀ but the trends in responses to acclimation temperatures differed between the two traits. Extreme acclimation temperatures (15 °C and 30 °C) had the most pronounced negative effects on percentage survival than the intermediate acclimation temperatures in the case of lower lethal temperature assays. In the case of upper lethal temperature assays, the general trend was that of an increase in percentage mortality with warmer acclimation temperatures, with the highest mortality rates recorded at 30 °C acclimation. These results suggest that there are costs associated with acclimation of the Argentine ant to extreme temperatures, as has been documented in other insects such as *Drosophila melanogaster* (Krebs and Loeschcke, 1994; Krebs and Feder, 1997; 1998). Therefore, although ecological niche models predict a broader distributional potential of the Argentine ant with global warming (Roura-Pascual et al., 2004), thermal tolerance

data presented here shows reduced survival of increasing temperatures implying that the distribution ranges of this species will be limited by high temperatures.

Furthermore, this Chapter provides data documenting the influence of exposure duration on both upper and lower lethal temperatures in the Argentine ant. In both traits, percentage mortality in the Argentine ant increased significantly with exposure duration. This is a clear indication that exposure time is an important factor in determining survivorship (Chown and Nicolson, 2004).

In Chapter 3, the effects of acclimation temperatures on critical thermal limits (assessed using a dynamic method) were investigated in the Argentine ant. However, unlike most other studies, this is the first study to have explicitly investigated the effects of experimental rates of temperature change on the outcome of acclimation for both upper and lower critical thermal limits. The data from this study showed that experimental rates of temperature change had several important and under-appreciated effects on critical thermal tolerances. First, while acclimation temperatures had a significant influence on both CT_{Max} and CT_{Min} , the magnitude of the acclimation responses were rate-dependent in both traits. Interestingly, the magnitude of acclimation response decreased with faster heating rates in CT_{Max} while the reverse was true for CT_{Min} . These results clearly show that upper and lower thermal limits differ in their responses to acclimation. Although previous studies have documented more flexibility in CT_{Min} than in CT_{Max} , (Gaston and Chown, 1999; Chown, 2001; Terblanche et al., 2007) this is the first study to provide data showing the influence of several rates of temperature change on the magnitude of acclimation responses in both traits.

Second, this study highlights the effects of rate of temperature change on inter-individual variability to trait responses. Inter-individual variability in both trait responses was greatest at the slowest rate of 0.05 °C/min and least at the fastest rate of 0.5 °C/min. In addition, the shape of frequency distributions changed significantly with rate of temperature change. These findings have important implications for further assessments of vital characteristics of thermal tolerance traits such as heritability (see Endler, 1986), which will be substantially affected by the methodological approach adopted.

Third, contrary to what several other studies have shown (Kelty and Lee, 1999, 2001; Rako and Hoffmann, 2006; Worland et al., 2007), slower rates of temperature

change did not result in improved thermal tolerances in the Argentine ant. This suggests that the Argentine ant does not show any hardening response.

The key findings of this thesis therefore include the following;

- Acclimation temperatures significantly influenced both critical thermal limits and lethal temperature outcome.
- The magnitude of acclimation responses, the shape of frequency distributions and the estimates of means and variances in critical thermal limits are all dependent on the experimental rate of temperature change used.
- The Argentine ant does not show any hardening response.
- Mortality increased significantly with exposure duration in lethal temperature assessments.

Recommendations for future studies

The Argentine ant is sensitive to moisture availability (Holway et al., 2002; Walters and Mackay, 2003). Hence, temperature and water are two of the most significant factors influencing its abundance and distribution (Holway et al., 2002; Roura-Pascual et al., 2004; Kruschelnycky et al., 2005; Hartley et al., 2006). The interactive effects of temperature and relative humidity on survival of the Argentine ant have not been explored and such studies are sorely needed to fully understand the environmental physiology of this invasive species.

The Argentine ant has been predicted to expand its distribution range with global warming (Roura-Pascual et al., 2004). Therefore an important trait to investigate in future studies is locomotion performance and its responses to different acclimation temperatures in the Argentine ant. Such studies will be useful in better understanding the influence of varying temperatures on their locomotion dependent activities such as dispersal, foraging and mate-finding.

Experimental studies on thermal tolerances of insects should involve a broader range of environmentally relevant temperature change rates in the region of 0.005 °C/min

to 0.01 °C/min will give a more robust indication of insects' responses to temperature fluctuations in the wild and how these responses may be influenced by global warming.

In the past few years, new techniques have been developed to measure the dynamic or behaviourally based thermal responses of animals in a more objective way. Such techniques include thermolimit respirometry (see Lighton and Garrigan, 1995; Lighton and Turner, 2004; Lighton, 2007) which combines metabolic rate measures along with activity. Therefore studies that include metabolic rate data of animals will be invaluable in identifying and investigating possible different mechanisms that come into play when temperature change rates vary significantly.

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